

PHYTOREMEDIATION OF POLLUTED AGRICULTURAL SOILS USING *TYPHA LATIFOLIA*

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ABSTRACT

Phytoremediation is a technology harnessing plants and their associated microbial communities to sequester harmful compounds in soil. This research aimed to restore contaminated soil, previously impacted by prolonged use of inorganic fertilizers, using *Typha latifolia* (broadleaf cattail). pH levels were assessed using a pH meter, while heavy metal concentrations were determined through Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry. *Typha latifolia*, commonly known as broadleaf cattail, was chosen for its remarkable capacity to absorb and accumulate metal ions. The experimental design comprised four individual pots: pots 1 and 2 were planted exclusively with *Typha latifolia*, while pots 3 and 4 functioned as control samples, consisting of uncontaminated soil without any plantings. Sampling was conducted in triplicate for each condition. The initial analysis of the polluted soil showed pH 5.4, carbon 2.0, nitrogen 1.40, iron 22.58, copper 1.06, manganese 4.22, and zinc 2.05 (mg/kg). Following treatment, the soil exhibited improved values, with pH 6.70, carbon 1.64, nitrogen 0.18, iron 7.69, copper 0.38, manganese 5.00, and zinc 0.99 (mg/kg), however, promising results were observed at the two and three-month marks during the four-month period of the research. The study advocates for the adoption of phytoremediation in agricultural soils and polluted lands, emphasizing its cost-effectiveness and emerging potential in land restoration.

Keywords: Phytoremediation, *Typha latifolia*, inorganic fertilizer, heavy metal, contaminated soil.

INTRODUCTION

Phytoremediation, coined from the Greek roots "Phyto," meaning plant, and "remedium," signifying restoration (Federle and Schwab, 2009), encompasses a collection of plant-based technologies. These technologies utilize either naturally occurring or genetically modified plants to cleanse contaminated environments (Burken and Schnoor, 2007). Phytoremediation comprises four distinct techniques (phyto-extraction, phyto-degradation, phyto-stabilization, and phyto-volatilization) employed in the remediation of metal-polluted soils, sediments, and water (Bento *et al.*, 2005). The treated soils can subsequently support the growth of various plant species, including sunflowers, broadleaf cattails, maize, and sorghum.

Phyto-extraction involves the absorption of metal ions from the soil and their translocation to different parts of the plant. Phyto-degradation, conversely, entails the breakdown of organic contaminants facilitated by enzymes released from the plant's roots. Phyto-stabilization employs plants to immobilize absorbed metal ions from contaminated soils, while phyto-volatilization extracts metal ions directly from the soil, releasing them into the atmosphere (Blaylock *et al.*, 2007). There is documented evidence of certain plants demonstrating the ability to tolerate and accumulate high concentrations of ions in contaminated soils (Madison, 2001). Consequently,

phytoremediation has been employed for decades in addressing environmental challenges in agricultural soils, silviculture, and horticulture (Blaylock *et al.*, 2007).

Drawing from the pilot-scale field work conducted by Conger and Portier (2007), which aimed to establish theoretical limits providing explanatory insights into the obtained results, their findings were complemented by subsequent laboratory research reported by Ferro *et al.* (2004). This underscores the importance of understanding environmental laws as they pertain to soils, process technologies, toxicology, and the management of contaminated soils through phytoremediation, which can serve as a cost-effective measure in reducing the uptake of chemical pollutants by crops (Cherian and Oliveira, 2005). Hence, intensified research in phytoremediation is imperative to address the pressing issues of contaminants in agriculture. The contamination of agricultural soil and its repercussions have had far-reaching effects on biodiversity, posing a significant threat to human health through the food chain. Additionally, practical and cost-effective strategies should be developed to minimize the uptake of contaminants by agricultural crops from polluted soils. Hence, in the present circumstances, it is crucial to conduct extensive research on various aspects pertaining to the escalating challenges of agricultural contaminants. The following areas require focused attention:

- i. Environmental awareness regarding contaminants in agriculture: It is imperative to raise awareness among individuals about the presence and effects of contaminants in agricultural practices.
- ii. Identification and impacts of different types of contaminants in agriculture: Understanding the sources and consequences of various contaminants, such as heavy metals, pesticides, herbicides, insecticides, organic and inorganic fertilizers, pathogens, nutrients, animal wastes, and nano-contaminants, is essential in order to address their detrimental effects on agricultural systems.
- iii. Management strategies for agricultural contaminants: Developing effective management strategies is crucial. This includes the implementation of well-planned and engineered applications, utilization of agricultural wastes, and the application of techniques like phytoremediation and bioremediation for mitigating the adverse effects of contaminants in agriculture.

By undertaking in-depth research in these areas, we can proactively address the pressing issues associated with agricultural contaminants and work towards sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural practices.

LITERRATURE REVIEW

2.1 Phytoremediation of Inorganics

Inorganic contaminants are mineral-based and unlike organics, they cannot be mineralised or degraded. Therefore, their remediation must be either physical removal, conversion into biologically inert form or stabilization (Cunningham and Philip, 2000). However, as physical removal cannot be fully accomplished, conversion into biological inert form and stabilization should be a priority. Some plants have the ability of accumulating, transferring or stabilizing inorganic compounds. For the latter, the plant species only need to be tolerant to the inorganic compounds and avoid uptake, while for the former, hyperaccumulator plants have shown to

accumulate high concentrations of inorganic compounds thereby removing the contaminants from the soil (Singh *et al.*, 2017). According to Baker, (2000) hyperaccumulators are plants (when growing in their natural habitat) with the ability to accumulate high concentration of metals without toxic effects when compared to other species or genotype and also the ratio of shoot to root or leaf to root concentration of metals accumulated is greater than one. Presently there are about 400 plants that hyperaccumulate metals. *Brassicaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Caryophyllaceae*, *Cyperaceae*, *Cunouniaceae*, *Fabaceae*, *Flacourtiaceae*, *Lamiaceae*, *Poaceae*, *Violaceae* and *Euphorbiaceae* dominates the 45 families (Prasad, 2010). Most of the hyperaccumulators accumulate nickel while, manganese, cadmium, zinc and cobalt are accumulated by some. *Thlaspii caerulescens*, which is a hyperaccumulator of zinc and cadmium, has been identified as one of the most studied hyperaccumulators (Hwang and Cutright, 2002).

Table 1: Selected examples of successful phytoremediation trial for inorganic contaminants

Pollutant	Soil concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)	Plant species	Growth condition	Ammendment /Fertiliser	Measure of success
Cu	Unknown	<i>Brassica juncea</i> <i>Zea mays</i>	Glasshouse	EDTANa	Removal of 54% Cu
Cu	1200	<i>Elsholtzia splendens</i>	Glasshouse, Field	Urea, KH ₂ PO ₄	Removal of 61% Cu
Cu, Lead, Mn, Zn	Cu- 640 Lead- 2400 Mn-27000 Zn- 7800	<i>Brassica juncea</i>	Greenhouse	None	Removal of 58% metals
Zn, Cd	Zn-25200 Cd- 170	<i>Thlaspi caerulescens</i>	Greenhouse	Compost	Removal of 52% metals
Cd, Zn, Lead	Cd- 20 Zn- 500 Lead- 1000	<i>Dianthus chinensis</i> , <i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i>	Greenhouse	EDTA	Removal of 50% metals greater with EDTA
Cr	10	<i>Trigonella foenumgraecum. L</i> , <i>Spinacia oleracea</i> , <i>Brassica campestris</i>	Glasshouse	None	Removal of 80% Cr
Zn, Ni	Ni- 109 Zn- 1300	<i>Salix sp</i> <i>Populus sp</i> <i>Alnus sp</i>	Field	N	Removal of 52% Zn and stabilization of Ni
Cd	1.6 (av)	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i>	Field	N	Removal of 63% metal

Source: Cooke, (2002)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

The study utilized the following materials:

- i. Soil: This refers to the upper layer of the Earth supporting plant growth, composed of a mixture of organic matter, minerals, gases, liquids, and organisms. The specific soil type chosen for this study is a combination of silt and clay.
- ii. Soil Auger: A manual tool commonly used to collect disturbed soil samples from the surface or shallow depths, as well as for drilling to deeper layers where soil samples can be obtained using a separate soil sampler or soil core sampler.
- iii. Pot: A cylindrical container used to hold the soil during the phytoremediation experiment. Ceramic pots will be employed for this study as they effectively retain the treated soil and accommodate the plants.
- iv. Vegetation: This refers to a specific species of plants considered as a whole, providing ground cover. In this study, particular plant species will be used for the phytoremediation experiment.

3.1.1 Description of the study site

The soil sample was obtained from the school farm of the Federal University of Technology, Minna, where yam and maize crops are frequently cultivated. Over an extended period, the site has been subjected to the application of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) fertilizers in the ratios of 20:10:10 and 15:15:10.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Determination of soil pollution

The soil analysis aimed to assess the extent of soil pollution resulting from the long-term use of inorganic fertilizers, aligning with objective one of the study. The technique of Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) was employed to examine the soil samples and determine the presence and concentration of pollutants within the soil. Two separate pots or bioreactors were used to collect the soil samples, which were then subjected to analysis for various physiochemical parameters. These parameters included the soil's chemical composition, specifically nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), copper (Cu), lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), and zinc (Zn). Additionally, measurements were taken for plant height, shoot height, and plant width as part of the analysis process.

3.3 Data Collection

Data collected from the plant species included measurements such as shoot height, plant height, and plant width. This data was recorded at two-week intervals throughout the entire project duration to monitor the growth and improvement of the plants. Statistical analysis of the data was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 23.0, and the results were further analysed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research commenced by conducting an analytical evaluation to detect the contaminants found in the agricultural soil due to the extended use of synthetic fertilizers. This assessment laid the groundwork for implementing the phytoremediation procedure. The findings derived from this

inquiry, pertinent to the study, are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: The outcome of the soil test conducted prior to analysis

Parameter	Values	Remark
pH	5.4	Strongly acidic
Organic carbon (OC)	2.08	Very high
Total nitrogen (TN)	1.40	Very high
Available phosphorus	15.08	Moderate
Calcium (Ca ²⁺)	1.44	Very low
Magnesium (Mg ²⁺)	1.04	Moderate
Potassium (K ⁺)	0.09	Very low
Sodium (Na ⁺)	0.09	Very low
Salinity	8.94	Moderate
Iron (Fe)	22.58	High
Copper (Cu)	1.06	High
Manganese (Mn)	34.22	Very high
Zinc (Zn)	2.05	High

*All values are in mg/kg except for pH in Co-Pt.

Table 3: The outcome of the analytical test conducted after a period of 30 days for the test

Runs	pH	Carbon	Nitrogen	Iron	Copper	Manganese	Zinc
1	5.52 ± 0.04 ^d	2.08 ± 0.02 ^d	1.36 ± 0.02 ^f	19.01 ± 0.02 ^c	1.02 ± 0.02 ^c	27 ± 0.01 ^f	2.04 ± 0.02 ^d
2	5.65 ± 0.03 ^e	2.03 ± 0.02 ^c	1.24 ± 0.02 ^c	19.75 ± 0.02 ^g	1 ± 0.01 ^c	25.83 ± 0.01 ^d	1.90 ± 0.02 ^c

*All values are in mg/kg except for pH in Co-Pt. Statistical significance was evaluated within columns by mean of ANOVA. Significance level p is 0.05.

Table 4: The outcome of the analytical test conducted after a period of 60 days for the test

Runs	pH	Carbon	Nitrogen	Iron	Copper	Manganese	Zinc
1	5.82 ± 0.04 ^c	2.03 ± 0.04 ^d	1.05 ± 0.01 ^c	16.03 ± 0.02 ^{de}	0.83 ± 0.01 ^c	16.60 ± 0.04 ^e	1.74 ± 0.03 ^b
2	5.71 ± 0.04 ^b	2.01 ± 0.02 ^c	1.06 ± 0.02 ^c	16.05 ± 0.02 ^{ef}	0.84 ± 0.01 ^c	17.01 ± 0.01 ^f	1.78 ± 0.03 ^{bc}

*All values are in mg/kg except for pH in Co-Pt. Statistical significance was evaluated within columns by mean of ANOVA. Significance level p is 0.05.

Table 5: The outcome of the analytical test conducted after a period of 90 days for the test

Runs	pH	Carbon	Nitrogen	Iron	Copper	Manganese	Zinc
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1	6.23 ± 0.03 ^b	1.48 ± 0.00 ^c	0.67 ± 0.02 ^c	15.13 ± 0.03 ^d	0.61 ± 0.01 ^b	11.01 ± 0.03 ^g	1.47 ± 0.04 ^c
2	6.21 ± 0.02 ^b	1.83 ± 0.04 ^{de}	0.68 ± 0.01 ^c	15.15 ± 0.02 ^{de}	0.64 ± 0.03 ^b	11.01 ± 0.01 ^g	1.50 ± 0.02 ^c

*All values are in mg/kg except for pH in Co–Pt. Statistical significance was evaluated within columns by mean of ANOVA. Significance level p is 0.05.

Table 5: The outcome of the analytical test conducted after a period of 120 days for the test

Runs	pH	Carbon	Nitrogen	Iron	Copper	Manganese	Zinc
1	6.68 ± 0.03 ^c	1.53 ± 0.01 ^b	0.15 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	7.55 ± 0.02 ^c	0.39 ± 0.04 ^b	5.98 ± 0.03 ^d	0.93 ± 0.04 ^b
2	6.70 ± 0.04 ^c	1.64 ± 0.01 ^{cd}	0.18 ± 0.01 ^b	7.69 ± 0.03 ^d	0.38 ± 0.03 ^b	5.00 ± 0.01 ^c	0.99 ± 0.01 ^c

*All values are in mg/kg except for pH in Co–Pt. Statistical significance was evaluated within columns by mean of ANOVA. Significance level p is 0.05.

4.1 Pollutant Removed from Soil (Percentage)

At specific time points, namely 30, 60, 90, and 120 days after the commencement of the experiment, the samples underwent thorough analysis. The outcomes obtained were then employed to assess the removal effectiveness, which acted as a gauge of the project's efficacy. The percentage of removal efficiency, as per the definition provided by the American Public Health Association (2005), was computed using the designated formula:

$$\% P. R = \frac{I_m - F_m}{I_m} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where, P. R = Pollutant Removed

F_m = Final metal concentration

I_m = Initial metal concentration

Table 6: Pollutant Removed (%)

Runs	pH (%)	Carbon (%)	Nitrogen (%)	Iron (%)	Copper (%)	Manganese (%)	Zinc (%)
1	19.57	84.07	86.03	56.44	60.78	74.63	50.49
2	17.17	18.72	84.68	56.76	53.00	72.98	46.84

4.2 Features of *Typha latifolia*

Figure 1: Graph of plant height against time *Typha latifolia*

Figure 2: Graph of plant width against time *Typha latifolia*

Figure 3: Graph of shoot height against time *Typha latifolia*

4.3 Discussions

The study focused on the treatment of soil that had been contaminated due to prolonged application of inorganic fertiliser. The soil samples collected from the site underwent soil tests, which revealed that certain parameters such as pH, organic carbon, total nitrogen, iron, copper, manganese, and zinc were present in levels harmful to the soil. The treatment process was carried out over a period of 120 days, and soil tests were conducted at 30-day intervals to monitor the progress of the remediation. The chosen plant species for the study, *Typha latifolia*, demonstrated the ability to survive under harsh conditions during the remediation process.

The initial 30 days of treatment demonstrated that the pollutants in the soil were being remediated, as confirmed by soil testing. However, significant progress in soil treatment was observed between days 60 and 90. The initial analysis of the polluted soil showed pH 5.4, carbon 2.0, nitrogen 1.40, iron 22.58, copper 1.06, manganese 4.22, and zinc 2.05 (mg/kg). Following treatment, the soil exhibited improved values, with pH 6.70, carbon 1.64, nitrogen 0.18, iron 7.69, copper 0.38, manganese 5.00, and zinc 0.99 (mg/kg). Insights into plant-microbe interactions and tailored approaches provide new avenues for enhancing the efficiency and applicability of phytoremediation techniques.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusions

Phytoremediation, an environmentally friendly and cost-effective technology, was employed in this study. The conclusions drawn from the project based on the findings are as follows:

- i. The initial assessment of soil pollution levels was conducted using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) before implementing the treatment.
- ii. The hyperaccumulating ability of these plants facilitated a rapid remediation process.
- iii. *Typha latifolia* exhibits a high growth rate and biomass production, further enhancing its capacity to uptake and sequester pollutants.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, the following recommendations can be proposed to promote the adoption and advancement of phytoremediation technology:

- i. It is recommended to begin any phytoremediation project by conducting an initial assessment of soil pollution levels using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS). This step is crucial for accurately gauging the extent of contamination and tailoring the remediation approach accordingly.
- ii. Consider incorporating hyperaccumulating plants in the remediation process. Their unique ability to accumulate contaminants at high concentrations can significantly expedite the remediation process, leading to more rapid and effective pollution reduction.
- iii. Given *Typha latifolia's* high growth rate and substantial biomass production, it is recommended to prioritize this species in phytoremediation projects. Its vigorous growth enhances its capacity to absorb and sequester pollutants, making it an excellent choice for remediating contaminated environments.

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